

Structural Analysis and Intrinsic Enzyme Mimicking Activities of Ligand-Free PtAg Nanoalloys

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Dedicated to Prof. Thalappil Pradeep on the occasion of his 60th Birthday

Nanozymes are nanomaterials with biocatalytic properties under physiological conditions and are one class of artificial enzymes to overcome the high cost and low stability of natural enzymes. However, surface ligands on nanomaterials will decrease the catalytic activity of the nanozymes by blocking the active sites. To address this limitation, ligand-free PtAg nano-clusters (NCs) are synthesized and applied as nanozymes for various enzyme-mimicking reactions. By taking advantage of the mutual interaction of zeolitic imidazolate frameworks (ZIF-8) and Pt precursors, a good dispersion of PtAg bimetal NCs with a diameter of 1.78 ± 0.1 nm is achieved with ZIF-8 as a template. The incorporation of PtAgNCs in the voids of ZIF-8 is confirmed with structural analysis using the atomic pair-distribution function and powder X-ray diffraction. Importantly, the PtAgNCs present good catalytic activity for various enzyme-mimicking reactions, including peroxidase-/catalase- and oxidase-like reactions. Further, this work compares the catalytic activity between PtAg NCs and PtAg nanoparticles with different compositions and finds that these two nanozymes present a converse dependency of Ag-loading on their activity. This study contributes to the field of nanozymes and presents a potential option to prepare ligand-free bimetal biocatalysts with sizes in the nanocluster regime.

1. Introduction

The term of “nanozyme,” described as “nanomaterials with enzyme-like properties,” defines a class of promising materials for biomimicking.^[1,2] Nanozymes possess various advantages such as robust stability, low cost, flexibility in composition and structure design, durability, and versatile catalytic activity over natural enzymes.^[3,4] Recently, enormous progress was achieved in utilizing noble metal-based nanomaterials like gold, platinum, and silver nanoparticles (NPs) as nanozymes.^[5–7] For example, Pt NP-based nanomaterials exhibit efficient enzyme mimetic activity such as ferroxidase-, oxidase (OD)-, and peroxidase (POD)-like mimics.^[6,8] Their properties are strongly dependent on the intrinsic nature of catalytically active metals (composition, size, morphology, and structure).^[9] Bimetallic nanoalloys may possess enhanced enzyme-mimicking activity

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due to synergistic effects.^[10,11] Gharib and colleagues synthesized bovine serum albumin (BSA)-capped AgPt NPs, exhibiting better pH-POD/catalase (CAT) mimicking activity than monometal NPs.^[12] Recent reports suggest that noble metal nanoclusters (NCs) can be an excellent choice of material for enzyme mimicking, and have been pursuing their analytical potential.^[13–16] In general, these metal NCs and NPs are protected by means of organic ligands (e.g., thiols, phosphines), which play many roles, especially in providing colloidal stability and solubility.^[17–19] However, ligands may also block the active sites on the metal surface, resulting in a decrease in the catalytic properties. Hence an improved method for the synthesis of ligand-free NCs and NPs without involving ligands would be desirable. Laser ablation is one possibility in this direction.^[20–22] Ligand-free synthesis has been also achieved by the wet-chemical approach by synthesizing the NPs/NCs in a template such as metal-organic frameworks, mesoporous silica, and metal oxides.^[23–26] However, controlling the particle size is one of the major challenges in such template-mediated synthesis.

The catalytic properties of monometal NCs can be further enhanced by doping with other metals. While recent studies indicate that proper alloying of Pt with Ag leads to dramatic enhancement of the catalytic activities, PtAg NCs-based nanozymes have been rarely explored.^[27–30] This might be due to the large miscibility gap of Pt and Ag metals at low temperature.^[31] The creation of ligand-free PtAg NCs remains a challenge and there is a need to improve the synthesis methodology for designing such nanozymes.

Herein, we reported a method for synthesizing ligand-free PtAg NC-based nanozymes which are formed in Zeolitic imidazolate framework (ZIF-8). Changes in synthesis parameters yielded PtAg alloys of different sizes and compositions. Pair distribution functions (PDF) analysis of X-ray total scattering data can give insights into the structure of amorphous and nanocrystalline NCs,^[32] NPs,^[33,34] and other materials.^[35–37] Combined PDF and powder X-ray diffraction (PXRD) analysis enabled an understanding of the local structure and incorporation of PtAg NCs within ZIF-8. Moreover, mimicking the activity of PtAg nanozymes with different sizes and compositions were evaluated.

2. Results and Discussion

To synthesize the PtAg nanozymes, two different approaches namely, a) co-reduction and b) a Pt-guided method were carried out (Scheme 1).^[24,31] In the co-reduction process K_2PtCl_4 and $AgNO_3$ precursors were introduced into the as-obtained ZIF-8 mixture (the experimental details are mentioned in the Supporting Information) and further reduced by $NaBH_4$. For the Pt-guided method, monometallic Pt@ZIF-8 was first formed, followed by the addition of K_2PtCl_4 and $AgNO_3$ reduced by $NaBH_4$ for further PtAg alloy preparation (the details are mentioned in Supporting Information). Here, the ZIF-8 pores are used as a template to form the Pt NCs, thus the growth of the NCs is restricted to the size of pores (1.85 nm in diameter). Most importantly, it has been demonstrated that the N-groups would anchor Pt atoms, which enables the Pt(IV) reduction in the pores of ZIF-8.^[38] Without ZIF-8, both Pt and Ag directly formed aggregates (Figure S1, Supporting Information). The resultant particles were characterized using transmission electron microscopy (TEM), high-resolution TEM (HRTEM), high-angle annular dark-field scanning transmission electron microscopy (HAADF-STEM), and energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS) mapping, which confirms the presence of both the metals. In all TEM images (Figure 1), the ZIF-8 nanocrystals present a rhombic dodecahedral shape as reported before.^[39] Interestingly, based on the Pt-guided method, we obtained smaller PtAg NCs, which had a homogeneous dispersion (Figure 1a,b), denoted as G-PtAgNCs-2 hereafter (2 represents the volume (unit: μL) of $AgNO_3$ used). The average core diameter of G-PtAgNCs-2 was $d_c = 1.78 \pm 0.12$ nm (Figure 1b, inset). A HRTEM image shows the lattice space of 0.230 nm, which can be ascribed to the fringes of the (111) plane in an individual G-PtAgNC-2 (Figure 1b, inset).^[40,41] G-PtAgNCs-2 are found to be slightly bigger in terms of size as compared to Pt@ZIF-8 ($d_c = 1.73 \pm 0.10$ nm, Figure S2, Supporting Information). The co-reduction method yielded bigger-sized PtAg NPs with $d_c = 9.10 \pm 2.31$ nm (Figure 1e,f), denoted as C-PtAgNPs_{4.5} (the subscript refers to the ratio of Ag to Pt). HRTEM data suggest that the C-PtAgNPs_{4.5} have lattice fringes spacings of 0.223 and 0.240 nm, which were ascribed to the (111) crystal planes

Scheme 1. Schematic illustration of the synthesis approaches of PtAg alloys via a) co-reduction and b) Pt-guided method.

Figure 1. a,b) TEM images and c,d) HAADF-STEM images of G-PtAgNCs-2 samples. The insets in b represent the corresponding size distribution histogram $N(d_c)$ of the core diameter ($d_c = 1.78 \pm 0.12$ nm) and the HRTEM of a PtAgNC. e,f) TEM images and g,h) HAADF-STEM images of C-PtAgNPs_{4,5} samples. The insets in (e,f) are the corresponding size distribution histograms of the core diameter ($d_c = 9.10 \pm 2.31$ nm) and a HRTEM image of a PtAgNP in C-PtAgNPs_{4,5} samples. i,j) Corresponding element mapping images of i) G-PtAgNCs-2 and j) C-PtAgNPs_{4,5}.

of *fcc* Pt NPs and Ag NPs, respectively (Figure 1f, inset).^[42,43] HAADF-STEM imaging and EDS elements mapping analyses were performed to elucidate more structural information and compositions. The structure of the PtAg alloy is particularly distinct in HAADF-STEM images for both G-PtAgNCs-2 (Figure 1c,d) and C-PtAgNPs_{4,5} (Figure 1g,h). The PtAg alloy has a brighter contrast as compared to the structure of ZIF-8, owing to the larger atomic mass of the elements Pt and Ag as compared to the Zn in ZIF-8. Figure 1c,d suggests the formation of smaller and uniform G-PtAgNCs-2 in ZIF-8, and Figure 1g,h shows the formation of the bigger size C-PtAgNPs_{4,5}. Elemental mapping shows the homogeneous distribution of Pt and Ag in both, G-PtAgNCs-2 and C-PtAgNPs_{4,5} (Figure 1i,j, respectively), indicating the successful formation of PtAg alloys. The Ag:Pt

ratios were higher for the case of C-PtAgNPs_{4,5} in comparison to G-PtAgNCs-2 as seen from their EDS spectra (Figure S3, Supporting Information).

While the data in Figure 1 confirm the presence of PtAg in ZIF-8, they do not provide 3D information. In order to figure out whether the PtAg alloys are growing only at the surface of ZIF-8 or also in the pores of ZIF-8, we performed PXRD studies. The PXRD patterns of ZIF-8 and C-PtAgNPs_{4,5} are identical as shown in Figure S5, Supporting Information. However, the PXRD pattern of the G-PtAgNCs-2 crystal structure differs significantly from the crystal structure of pristine ZIF-8 (Figure 2a). Additional reflexes in the PXRD pattern of G-PtAgNCs-2 were observed in the range from 10 to 30°. Interestingly, we can exclude the formation of an additional

Figure 2. The characterization of G-PtAgNCs-2 with X-ray scattering methods. a) PXRD data of the angle-dependent scattering intensity $I(Q)$ of G-PtAgNCs-2 as compared with ZIF-8. The arrows highlight the differences between both datasets at 11.2° , 16.9° , 19.0° , and 24.1° the corresponding lattice planes which suggest a periodic ordering of G-PtAgNCs-2 in ZIF-8. b) PDF analysis simulating the intensity of atomic pair correlations $G(r)$ by a two-phase refinement of the PtAg fcc and ZIF-8 phase reveals a good agreement of the experimental PDF (G_{trunc}) with the calculated PDF (G_{calc}) ($R_w = 0.19$) besides a mismatch at 4.2 \AA , highlighted by the difference curve (G_{diff}). Since the two-phase refinement considers two separated phases, the mismatch could correspond to the pair-correlation of Zn in ZIF-8 to a Pt/Ag atom of the ordered G-PtAgNCs-2. c) Proposed structure in which G-PtAgNCs-2 are filling the void in a cubic ZIF-8 structure with the space group $I\bar{4}3m$.

crystalline phase. Instead, we index the additional reflexes to lattice planes through the unit cell of ZIF-8 if additionally, a Pt atom was inserted (Figure S4, Supporting Information). This

finding strongly suggests that the NCs grow inside the pores of ZIF-8.

To further test this hypothesis, we perform a PDF analysis. The PDF analysis confirms the size of G-PtAgNCs-2 to be $\approx 1.9 \text{ nm}$, which is similar to the size obtained with TEM ($1.78 \pm 0.12 \text{ nm}$) and which is smaller than the size of the pores in ZIF-8 (details are available in Supporting Information). Moreover, two-phase refinement analysis on the G-PtAgNCs-2 shows the presence of the two crystalline phases from G-PtAgNCs-2 and from ZIF-8 with good agreement shown by a relatively small mismatch ($R_w = 0.19$) in Figures S10 and S11, Supporting Information. It only fails to describe the peak at $\approx 4.5 \text{ \AA}$, which points out that there is an additional ordering, not described by the two individual phases. We assign this peak to the interatomic distance between Zn atoms and Pt/Ag clusters within the ZIF-8 as schematically illustrated in Figure 2c. This further supports the hypothesis that G-PtAgNCs grow within the pores of ZIF-8.

The N_2 absorption-desorption isotherms of the as-obtained ZIF-8, G-PtAgNCs-2, and C-PtAgNPs_{4.5} samples indicated the typical microporous structures of ZIF-8-based materials (Figure S12a, Supporting Information). A slight decrease in both, surface areas and pore volumes, were observed in G-PtAgNCs-2 and C-PtAgNPs_{4.5} samples compared as to ZIF-8, which can be deduced from the integrated PtAg. The Brunauer–Emmett–Teller surface areas (S_{BET}) of G-PtAgNCs-2 and C-PtAgNPs_{4.5} were 1471 and $1412 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$, and pore volumes were 0.5876 and $0.5124 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ g}^{-1}$, respectively, compared to $1733 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ and $0.6525 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ g}^{-1}$ of ZIF-8 (Figure S12b and Table S2, Supporting Information). This is expected because of the nonporous bimetallic PtAg on/in the structure of ZIF-8.

X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) was carried out to analyze the surface compositions and valence states for both, G-PtAgNCs-2 and C-PtAgNPs_{4.5} in comparison with pristine ZIF-8 (Figure S13a, Supporting Information). The Zn 2p signal of G-PtAgNCs-2 and C-PtAgNPs_{4.5} was deconvoluted into two components, the lower energy band (Zn $2p_{3/2}$) at 1021.8 and 1023.5 eV for G-PtAgNCs-2, and 1021.5 and 1022.7 eV for C-PtAgNPs_{4.5}, whereas a high energy band (Zn $2p_{1/2}$) at 1044.5 and 1046.2 eV for G-PtAgNCs-2, and 1044.6 and 1045.9 eV for C-PtAgNPs_{4.5}, respectively (Figure 3a). This indicated that Zn is present in two different oxidation states, Zn (0) and Zn (II). In comparison with those in pure ZIF-8, positive shifts to higher binding energy were observed after PtAg alloy formation for both samples.^[39] The XPS spectrum of N 1s for G-PtAgNCs-2 and C-PtAgNPs_{4.5} showed a shift to higher binding energy as compared to that in Pt@ZIF-8 in Figure S13b, Supporting Information and the pristine ZIF-8.^[24] This implies the existence of an interaction between Pt, Ag with N, and Zn after the introduction of PtAg alloy in ZIF-8. Notably, the Pt 4f spectrum of G-PtAgNCs-2 and C-PtAgNPs_{4.5} had a strong doublet at 70.8 and 74.05 eV for G-PtAgNCs-2, while 70.7 and 74.05 eV for C-PtAgNPs_{4.5} are the characteristic peaks of Pt $4f_{7/2}$ and Pt $4f_{5/2}$, respectively (Figure 3b). A negative shift was observed in both samples as compared to the Pt 4f spectra in Pt@ZIF-8 (Figure S13c, Supporting Information). Together with the binding energy of Ag 3d spectrum peaks displayed in Figure 3c, which show higher binding energy shift in both, G-PtAgNCs-2 and C-PtAgNPs_{4.5} samples, as compared to standard Ag, this

Figure 3. a–c) High-resolution XPS spectra of a) Zn, b) Ag, and c) Pt of i) C-PtAgNPs_{4,5} and ii) G-PtAgNCs-2, showing the emission intensity versus the binding energy $I(E_B)$.

confirmed the successful formation of the PtAg alloy in ZIF-8 and an electron transfer from Ag to Pt due to the higher metallic electronegativity of Pt compared to that of Ag.^[29,44] Furthermore, thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) showed that for the G-PtAgNCs and C-PtAgNPs the weight loss starts only at temperatures higher than 500 °C, which is much higher than that of 2-MeIM we used in the synthesis (Figure S14, Supporting

Information). Thus, this indicates that no organic ligands are adsorbed at the surface of G-PtAgNCs and C-PtAgNPs.

The different PtAg nanomaterials were then examined for their catalytic activity in respect to different enzyme mimics such as POD, CAT, and OD-like activities (Figure 4a). The POD-like catalytic activities of PtAg nanoalloys were evaluated with *o*-phenylenediamine (OPD) as the chromogenic substrate. Both, C-PtAgNPs_{4,5} and G-PtAgNCs-2, could induce the oxidation of OPD to the yellow oxidized product 2,3-diaminophenazine (DAP) at 450 nm in the presence of H₂O₂ (Figure S15, Supporting Information). The optimal condition of pH 4 was observed for POD-like activities of

G-PtAgNCs-2 and C-PtAgNPs_{4,5} (Figure S16, Supporting Information). The composition-dependent POD-like activity of ligand-free PtAg nanoalloys was investigated further to understand the role of the individual elements. For the C-PtAgNP samples, six other samples with different molar ratio of Pt:Ag (1:0.5, 1:1, 1:2, 1:3, 1:3.5, and 1:4) were prepared, referred to as C-PtAgNPs_{0.5}, C-PtAgNPs₁, C-PtAgNPs₂, C-PtAgNPs₃, C-PtAgNPs_{3.5}, and C-PtAgNPs₄, respectively. Similarly, different volumes of AgNO₃ (4, 8, 16, 32, 40, and 80 μL) were used to prepare the G-PtAgNC samples, denoted here as G-PtAgNCs-4, G-PtAgNCs-8, G-PtAgNCs-16, G-PtAgNCs-32, G-PtAgNCs-40, and G-PtAgNCs-80, respectively (Figures S17–S19, Supporting Information). It is observed that G-PtAgNCs-2 with lower Ag:Pt ratio have the better POD-like activities (Figure S20a,b, Supporting Information), whereas in the contrast, C-PtAgNPs_{4,5} with a higher Ag:Pt ratio show the higher catalytic properties (Figure S20c,d, Supporting Information). Subsequently, the colorimetric 3,3',5,5'-tetramethylbenzidin (TMB) substrate was applied to investigate the OD-like activity of the PtAg nano alloys in the presence of dissolved O₂ (Figure S21, Supporting Information). Compared with other control nanomaterials, G-PtAgNCs-2 could fast catalyze the oxidation of TMB to generate the blue color oxidized TMB (oxTMB) with absorption centered at 652 nm (Figure S22, Supporting Information), while the C-PtAgNPs_{4,5} samples exhibited negligible OD-like properties, probably because of the higher Ag:Pt ratio in C-PtAgNPs_{4,5} as compared to that in G-PtAgNCs-2. Further, the optimal pH for the TMB oxidation under the catalysis of G-PtAgNCs-2 was ≈ 4 and thus similar to the one of the OPD oxidation (Figure S23, Supporting Information). This might be due to the similar diamine structure in both substrates due to which they exhibited poor solubility under weak alkaline conditions,^[45,46] indicating that the pH-dependent catalytic property was not associated with nanocatalysts themselves, but to the substrates. Similar to the OPD-like measurement, we also found that the sample with lower Ag:Pt ratio (G-PtAgNCs-2) has the better catalytic activity (Figures S24 and S25, Supporting Information).

In addition, the PtAg nanoalloys could induce the decomposition of H₂O₂ to produce O₂ simultaneously, confirming that the PtAg nanoalloys have CAT-like activity (Figure S26, Supporting Information). We found that the catalysts with lower Ag:Pt ratio (i.e., G-PtAgNCs-2, G-PtAgNCs-4) or higher Ag:Pt ratio (i.e., C-PtAgNPs_{4,5}) show the better catalytic performance (Figure S27, Supporting Information), and the optimal reaction condition is found in neutral solution (Figure S28, Supporting Information).

Figure 4. a) Schematic illustration of the enzyme mimicking process of POD-like, CAT-like, and OD-like activity by G-PtAgNCs-2 (left) and C-PtAgNPs_{4.5} (right). b, c) Corresponding K_m and v_{max} analysis of Pt@ZIF-8, Ag@ZIF-8, G-PtAgNCs-2, and C-PtAgNPs_{4.5} for the enzyme mimicking.

The apparent steady-state kinetics of their enzyme-like activities were investigated. The kinetic data were recorded with varying one substrate concentration, whereas keeping the other substrate concentration constant. The initial reaction rates (ν) were calculated and typical Michaelis–Menten curves were obtained by plotting the reaction rate with the substrate concentration (Figures S30–S43, Supporting Information). Based on the double reciprocal of the Michaelis–Menten equation, Lineweaver–Burk plots of $1/\nu$ and $1/c_S$ were constructed, $1/\nu = (K_m/\nu_{max}) \times (1/c_S) + 1/\nu_{max}$, where ν is the initial velocity, c_S is the concentration of substrate, K_m is the Michaelis–Menten constant and ν_{max} is the maximal reaction velocity.^[47] Generally, a lower K_m value represents a higher affinity between the enzyme and substrate.^[48] The kinetic parameters (K_m and ν_{max}) were calculated by using Lineweaver–Burk plots are summarized in Figure 4b,c and in Table S3, Supporting Information. The K_m value of the G-PtAgNCs-2 with H₂O₂ substrate in both POD-/CAT-like activities is higher than that of HRP. This is consistent with the observation that a higher concentration of H₂O₂ was required to obtain maximal activity of G-PtAgNCs-2. The lowest K_m value (0.231 mM) of G-PtAgNCs-2 with OPD was observed among HRP (0.59 mM) and the others, implying a higher affinity of G-PtAgNCs-2 to OPD substrate than those of the others. This is probably due to the presence of more “active sites” on the surface of ligand-free G-PtAgNCs-2 in comparison to HRP. For a quantitative comparison (Table S3, Supporting Information), the specific activity parameter ν'_M of metal-based nanozymes was introduced, which was defined as the activity per mass (μg) of the specific metal ($\nu'_M = \nu_{max}/m_M$, where m_M is the total mass of the metal Pt or Ag added in the reaction, unit: $\mu\text{M s}^{-1} \mu\text{g}^{-1}_M$). For G-PtAgNCs-2 catalysts, the ν'_{Pt} and ν'_{Ag} values for POD-/CAT-/OD-like activities were cal-

culated to be higher than those of Pt@ZIF-8 and Ag@ZIF-8 catalysts, indicating that G-PtAgNCs-2 possess enhanced enzyme mimics activities. In addition, the ν'_{Ag} values were calculated to be 83 and 46 (with H₂O₂ and OPD substrate, respectively), 36 900, and 4390 $\mu\text{M s}^{-1} \mu\text{g}^{-1}_{Ag}$ for POD-, CAT-, and OD-like activities, respectively, which was ≈ 100 times higher than those of ν'_{Pt} . This may imply that doping with Ag contributes to enhanced catalytic properties.

It can be found that the POD-/OD-/CAT-like activity of G-PtAgNCs-2/G-PtAgNCs-4 and C-PtAgNPs_{4.5} (higher ν' values) are obviously higher than those of the monometal Pt@ZIF-8 and Ag@ZIF-8 nanozymes (Table S3, Supporting Information). These results suggest that the catalytic property of G-PtAgNCs-2 is related to the synergistic effect of alloying, as reported previously in literature, that would contribute to the enhanced catalytic efficiency.^[28,30] The synergistic effect of Ag-Pt has been elaborated for various reactions and devices in previous reports. For example, Chen et al. found that a high catalytic performance for CO selective oxidation was triggered by Pt-Ag interactions.^[49] In another study, Cai et al. developed porous Pt/Ag NPs, which present remarkable enhancement in multiple enzyme-mimic activities due to synergistic Pt-Ag interaction.^[50] Another interesting observation is that for NC alloys the optimal catalyst behavior is with lower Ag:Pt ratio, suggesting that trace Ag doping would induce the largest enhancement.^[31] This may be attributed to that Ag presents a single atom type and interacts with Pt in the NCs to provide a synergistic effect, however, high Ag loading would lead to Ag-Ag bonds and weaken the synergistic effect. To confirm the Ag-Ag bond formation at the high Ag loading, we measured the UV–vis absorption spectra of the PtAg NCs and the Pt NCs. As shown in Figure S44, Supporting Information, for

high Ag loadings (G-PtAgNCs-32 and G-PtAgNCs-80) we found molecule-like features in the UV–vis absorption spectra. Such molecule-like absorption features of the high-Ag-loading samples are due to the formation of Ag NCs.^[51–53] Ag–Ag bond formations are reported in all structurally solved AgNCs reported so far. Hence, the formation of AgNCs strongly supports the existence of Ag–Ag bonds at higher Ag-loading. On the other hand, for the NPs alloys, the optimal catalyst is the sample with the highest Ag:Pt ratio. This is because in the C-PtAgNPs_{4,5}, both, Pt and Ag formed the larger particles and the synergistic effect only occurs at the interface between Pt and Ag, the sample with a larger ratio of Ag:Pt suggests more interface and high Pt atom usage. To further demonstrate the advantage of the ligand-free strategy as enzyme mimics, we compared their kinetic parameters with those of other metal NP-based nanozymes with surface ligands (Table S3, Supporting Information). Unsurprisingly, the ligand-free G-PtAgNCs-2 and C-PtAgNPs_{4,5} also exhibit higher enzymatic properties than those ligand-protected Pt NPs.^[8,54] This may imply that the catalytic activity is related to the surface properties and that ligands would block the active sites of the NPs catalysts surface (Figure S29, Supporting Information). In addition to the synergistic effect and surface effect, the enzyme mimics activity might be related to size distribution. As we found, in our case, the smaller G-PtAgNCs-2 possess superior enzymatic activity than the bigger C-PtAgNPs_{4,5}, mainly due to the larger surface-to-volume ratios and more exposed “active sites” on the metal surface. Two possible catalytic mechanisms were proposed: the generation of radical intermediates ($\cdot\text{OH}$, $\cdot\text{O}_2^-$), and the generation of efficient electron transfer intermediates to facilitate electron transfer among substrates.^[48,55,56] To figure out which mechanism dominates the catalytic process of our nanozymes, more assays were used to detect the intermediates during the reaction. First, for the POD-like activities, terephthalic acid (TA) was chosen as a fluorescence probe to detect $\cdot\text{OH}$, which will yield the highly fluorescent product 2-hydroxy terephthalic acid when reacted with $\cdot\text{OH}$.^[57–59] When the G-PtAgNCs-2 were added to the mixture of H_2O_2 and TA, no increase in fluorescence intensity was observed, and fluorescence even decreased with the concentration of G-PtAgNCs-2 increasing (Figure S45, Supporting Information). This indicates that no free $\cdot\text{OH}$ was formed during the G-PtAgNCs-2 catalytic process in the presence of H_2O_2 . Another fluorescence probe, hydroethidine (HE), was added into the O_2 -saturated buffer solution to detect $\cdot\text{O}_2^-$ for the OD-like activity of G-PtAgNCs-2. No pronounced fluorescent emission at 610 nm was observed at both, pH 4 and pH 7 buffer solutions, suggesting very limited free $\cdot\text{O}_2^-$ formed under these conditions (Figure S46, Supporting Information). Therefore, we indicated that the nature of the enzyme mimics the catalytic behavior of our G-PtAgNCs-2 does not dominantly originate from the generation of $\cdot\text{OH}$ or $\cdot\text{O}_2^-$ radicals. It is probably due to their ability of accelerating electron-transfer processes between the substrates and H_2O_2 or O_2 .

3. Conclusion

In summary, we have prepared ligand-free PtAg bimetal NCs with narrow size distribution and proved that these nanomate-

rials have excellent POD-/OD-/CAT-like activities like enzymes. We also presented a way to differentiate between PtAg NCs inside the ZIF-8 framework and PtAg NPs at the surface of the ZIF-8 framework by combining PXRD, PDF, and TEM analysis. By investigating the size- and composition-dependent activity, we found that trace Ag doping in Pt NCs would greatly enhance the catalytic activity, which could be attributed to the synergistic effect between Pt and Ag. Further, the mechanism investigation shows that the mechanism of our enzyme mimicking reaction may follow a pathway of accelerating the electron-transfer process between the substrates and H_2O_2 or O_2 . This study enriches the toolbox to prepare ligand-free nanozymes based on bimetal NCs and the finding of the converse dependency of the ratio of Ag:Pt on activity for nanozymes with different sizes suggests that a lower Ag:Pt ratio may contribute to higher catalytic properties.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available in the supplementary material of this article.

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enzyme mimicking, nanoalloys, nanoclusters, nanoparticles, pair-distribution function, powder X-ray diffraction analysis

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